

An Optimization-Based Framework for State Bounds of Parametric ODE Solutions

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Abstract. For a parametric system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs), we consider the construction of state bounding trajectories that provide interval lower/upper bounds on each component of all ODE solution trajectories simultaneously. State bounds are useful in their own right as reachable set enclosures, and are also critical within modern deterministic relax-then-discretize methods for global dynamic optimization. We present a new general framework for describing state bounds, based on optimal-value functions involving bounds on the original ODE’s right-hand side. We show that many existing state bounding methods can be recovered in our framework, along with several useful new methods as well. Numerical examples are also presented, based on a proof-of-concept implementation in Julia.

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1. Introduction

As considered by Scott and Barton (2013) and others, typical methods for global dynamic optimization involve computing appropriate upper and lower bounds on the optimal value on several subdomains within a branch-and-bound framework. In this context, typical lower-bounding methods involve constructing and minimizing a relevant convex relaxation, which in turn requires bounding information and convex relaxation information regarding the embedded dynamic model.

In this manuscript, we consider dynamic models represented as parametric systems of ordinary differential equations (ODEs). Several established methods can generate reachable set bounds for ODEs; these have been categorized into *discretize-then-relax* and *relax-then-discretize* approaches. In discretize-then-relax approaches (such as by Esposito and Floudas (2000), Lin and Stadtherr (2007), Sahlodin and Chachuat (2011)), the ODEs are discretized in time and replaced by an approximating closed-form function or equation system, which is then typically bounded by standard approaches underlying the global optimization solvers BARON (Sahinidis 1996) and ANTIGONE (Misener and Floudas 2014). As considered by Scott and Barton (2013), Song and Khan (2021), typical relax-then-discretize approaches express an ODE’s reachable set as the solution of an auxiliary ODE system, which can then be solved using ODE solvers. One benefit of this approach is that it preserves the ODE solvers’ useful adaptive time-stepping features and error control features.

State bounds for a parametric ODE are special trajectories that encode lower and upper bounds on each component of the solution of the underlying ODE. To our knowledge, all existing relax-then-discretize approaches for parametric ODEs depend on the ability to compute state bounds. Several state bounding techniques have been proposed; many of which depend on fundamental approaches and observations by Walter (1970), Harrison (1977).

This manuscript introduces a new state bounding framework, that includes many established bounding methods and suggests several useful new bounding methods as well. The remainder of this manuscript is structured as follows. Section 2 lays out our mathematical problem formulation.

Section 3 presents our new bounding framework, and Section 4 presents several bounding methods within this framework, including several established methods, some new methods based on *generalized McCormick relaxations* of Scott et al. (2011), and a new method based on the *edge-concave relaxations* of Hasan (2018). Section 5 presents numerical examples based on a proof-of-concept implementation of our methods in the programming language Julia.

2. Problem Formulation

We consider essentially the same formulation as Ye and Scott (2025). Consider scalars $t_0, t_f \in \mathbb{R}$ with $t_0 < t_f$. Consider the following sets:

- a duration of interest: $I := [t_0, t_f]$,
- an interval containing permitted parameter values: $P \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$, and
- a nonempty open set containing permitted state values: $D \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$,

and consider two Lipschitz continuous functions: an initial condition mapping $\mathbf{x}_0 : P \rightarrow D$ and a vector field mapping $\mathbf{f} : I \times P \times D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$.

The remainder of this article considers the following parametric ordinary differential equation (ODE) system. Suppose that for each $\mathbf{p} \in P$, there exists a solution $t \mapsto \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p})$ on I of the ODE initial-value problem:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{x}(t_0, \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{x}_0(\mathbf{p}). \quad (1)$$

According to the Picard-Lindelöf Theorem (as stated by Hartman (2002, Theorem 1.1, Chapter II)), the parametric ODE solution $\mathbf{x} : I \times P \rightarrow D$ is unique.

Our goal is to formulate new types of useful *state bounds* for the ODE system (1), namely functions $\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U : I \rightarrow D$ for which:

$$\mathbf{x}^L(t) \leq \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p}) \leq \mathbf{x}^U(t), \quad \forall t \in I, \quad \mathbf{p} \in P. \quad (2)$$

(Throughout this article, inequalities involving vectors apply componentwise.) State bounds enclose the reachable set of (1), and are a critical component within several recent approaches for generating convex/concave relaxations of $\mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p})$ with respect to \mathbf{p} , for use in dynamic global optimization (Scott and Barton 2013, Song and Khan 2021, Ye and Scott 2025). In this setting, intuitively, we require state bounds that are mathematically guaranteed to satisfy (2), and we would additionally benefit from having state bounds that are tighter, computationally cheaper to evaluate, and that can be generated and computed automatically.

In the remainder of this manuscript, we will present a new framework for generating useful state bounds, and we will present several state bound formulations within this framework. Each of these formulations requires additional assumptions regarding the functions \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{x}_0 ; these will be described below.

3. New bounding framework

We propose a new framework for constructing state bounds for the ODE (1), in the sense of (2). Our framework requires functions $\mathbf{f}^L, \mathbf{f}^U$ that satisfy the following definition.

DEFINITION 1 (ENCLOSING DYNAMICS). Consider the setup of Section 2. Functions $\mathbf{f}^L, \mathbf{f}^U : I \times P \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ exhibit *enclosing dynamics* about \mathbf{x} if for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n_x\}$, almost all $t \in I$, all $\mathbf{p} \in P$, and all $\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U \in D$ for which $\mathbf{z}^L \leq \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p}) \leq \mathbf{z}^U$, both of the following conditions hold:

- If $z_i^L = x_i(t, \mathbf{p})$, then $f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) \leq f_i(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p}))$.
- If $z_i^U = x_i(t, \mathbf{p})$, then $f_i^U(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) \geq f_i(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p}))$.

Observe that this definition is very similar to the two definitions of *bound-preserving dynamics* presented by Scott and Barton (2013), Ye and Scott (2024); the primary difference is that our definition is fundamentally tied to the parametric ODE solution \mathbf{x} . As we will show later, there are several practical ways to construct functions that exhibit enclosing dynamics about \mathbf{x} , based on knowledge of the ODE (1).

Our main result is as follows; it employs enclosing dynamics to construct state bounds for (1).

THEOREM 1 (Bounding framework). *Consider values $\mathbf{x}_0^L, \mathbf{x}_0^U \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ for which $\mathbf{x}_0^L \leq \mathbf{x}_0(\mathbf{p}) \leq \mathbf{x}_0^U$ for each $\mathbf{p} \in P$. Suppose functions $\mathbf{f}^L, \mathbf{f}^U : I \times P \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ exhibit enclosing dynamics about \mathbf{x} . Suppose as well that $\mathbf{f}^L, \mathbf{f}^U$ are continuous, and that $\mathbf{f}^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U)$ and $\mathbf{f}^U(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U)$ are both locally Lipschitz continuous with respect to $(\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U)$, uniformly over $t \in I$ and $\mathbf{p} \in P$.*

Consider the following auxiliary coupled ODE system. For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n_x\}$ and $\mathbf{p} \in P$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_i^L &= \min_{\mathbf{p} \in P} f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U), & x_i^L(t_0) &= x_{0,i}^L, \\ \dot{x}_i^U &= \max_{\mathbf{p} \in P} f_i^U(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U), & x_i^U(t_0) &= x_{0,i}^U. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Then, this ODE has a unique solution $\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, and this solution comprises state bounds for the original ODE (1) in the sense of (2).

Proof Consider the right-hand side functions of the auxiliary ODE (3):

$$g_i^L(t, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U) := \min_{\mathbf{p} \in P} f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U), \quad g_i^U(t, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U) := \max_{\mathbf{p} \in P} f_i^U(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U).$$

By (Hu and Papageorgiou 1997, Theorem 3.4), these right-hand sides are continuous. Moreover, they are locally Lipschitz continuous with respect to $(\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U)$, uniformly over $t \in I$, due to the analogous local Lipschitz continuity of \mathbf{f}^L and \mathbf{f}^U . Hence, according to standard ODE theory, the ODE (3) does indeed have a unique solution $(\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U)$.

Next, applying the bounding result (Song and Khan 2025, Theorem 2) with the substitutions $\mathbf{v}^A := \mathbf{x}^L$, $\mathbf{v}^B := \mathbf{w}^B := \mathbf{x}(\cdot, \mathbf{p})$, and $\mathbf{w}^A := \mathbf{x}^U$, it immediately follows that $\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{x}^U$ are state bounds for the ODE (1). \square

The recent optimization-based bounding framework (3) superficially resembles a previous optimization-based formulation for convex relaxations for \mathbf{x} , as stated in (Song and Khan 2021, Equation 9). However, the two methods are significantly different: the embedded optimization problem by Song and Khan (2021) optimizes over the state variable \mathbf{x} , whereas the optimization problems embedded in (3) have \mathbf{p} as the decision variable. Moreover, that previous result does not intrinsically describe state bounds, and our new framework in (3) does not require convexity in any sense. Singer and Barton (2006) presented several bounding methods in a similar context; most are unrelated to our approach (as they again involve minimization with respect to \mathbf{x} rather than \mathbf{p}), though we note below that one of their methods is indeed recovered in our new framework.

4. Obtaining state bounds in our new framework

In this section, we obtain several specific types of state bounds within the bounding framework provided by Theorem 1. First, we provide some relevant background information regarding interval analysis, and then we list several existing bound formulations that can be obtained in our framework. Next, we construct new formulations and establish their useful properties.

4.1. Additional background information

Several of the formulations in the remaining sections make use of concepts from interval analysis and bounding theory that we will briefly introduce here. As described by Moore et al. (2009), an *interval* in \mathbb{R}^n is a set $\{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n : \mathbf{a} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}\}$ for vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with $\mathbf{a} \leq \mathbf{b}$. Such an interval may also be expressed as $[\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}]$. *Interval arithmetic* is a technique for outer-estimating the range of a function $\mathbf{g} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ when restricted to an interval subdomain $X \subset \mathbb{R}^n$; when \mathbf{g} is a finite composition of well-understood operations from a library, then interval arithmetic will typically construct *interval extension* bounds $\mathbf{g}^{IA,L}(X), \mathbf{g}^{IA,U}(X)$ for which:

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \in [\mathbf{g}^{IA,L}(X), \mathbf{g}^{IA,U}(X)], \quad \forall \mathbf{x} \in X.$$

Interval arithmetic approaches are typically *inclusion monotonic*: if we have two subdomain intervals $X, Y \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with $Y \subset X$, then we will also have:

$$[\mathbf{g}^{IA,L}(Y), \mathbf{g}^{IA,U}(Y)] \subset [\mathbf{g}^{IA,L}(X), \mathbf{g}^{IA,U}(X)].$$

Previous work by Harrison (1977), Scott and Barton (2013) made use of the following *flattening operations*, and we will use them too. Given an interval $[\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}] \in \mathbb{R}^n$, define

$$B_i^L([\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}]) := [\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{c}],$$

where $c_i = a_i$, but $c_j = b_j$ for each $j \neq i$. Similarly, define

$$B_i^U([\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}]) := [\mathbf{e}, \mathbf{b}],$$

where $e_i = b_i$, but $e_j = a_j$ for each $j \neq i$.

The *generalized McCormick relaxations* (Scott et al. 2011, Wechsung et al. 2015) use a similar approach to interval arithmetic to ultimately propagate convex relaxations and concave relaxations of functions that are amenable to interval analysis. This method is implemented in the automatic convex relaxation packages **MC++** (Chachuat 2014) and **McCormick.jl** (Wilhelm and Stuber 2020). Essentially, each input/output \mathbf{w} of the relaxed function is replaced with a corresponding *McCormick object*: a pair of intervals $([\mathbf{w}^{GM,L}, \mathbf{w}^{GM,U}], [\mathbf{w}^{GM,cv}, \mathbf{w}^{GM,cc}])$, the first of which contains interval bounds on \mathbf{w} , and the second of which is intended to contain convex and concave relaxation values for \mathbf{w} .

Lastly, we briefly summarize the *edge-concave* underestimation approach by Hasan (2018). Given a twice-continuously differentiable function $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on an interval subdomain $X \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ with midpoint \mathbf{x}^{mid} , an edge-concave underestimator of g on X is given by:

$$g^{EC,L}(\mathbf{x}) := g(\mathbf{x}) - \sum_{i=1}^{n_x} \theta_i^L (x_i - x_i^{mid})^2,$$

for coefficients $\theta_i^L > 0$ sufficiently large that each “cross-section” $x_i \mapsto g^{EC,L}(\mathbf{x})$ is concave. Hasan presents methods for automatically computing appropriate values of θ_i^L . Qualitatively, since edge-concave underestimators have a very different graph shape than convex underestimators, there are cases where edge-concave underestimators can be much closer to the underestimated function than the best possible convex underestimator.

4.2. Recovering established bounding methods

In this section, we briefly note several established bounding approaches that can be obtained in the state bounding framework of Theorem 1. Hence, our framework generalizes and unifies all of these approaches. We assume that the problem setup of Section 2 is in effect. In each case it is straightforward to prove that enclosing dynamics are indeed upheld, in the sense of Definition 1.

- Suppose f and x_0 are locally Lipschitz continuous and have inclusion monotonic interval extensions. An interval-based bounding method motivated by Harrison (1977) and used by Scott and Barton (2013) is recovered in (3) by setting:

ATTENTION: The following displayed equation, in its current form, exceeds the column width that will be used in the published edition of your article. Please break or rewrite this equation to fit, including the equation number, within a column width of 470 pt / 165.81 mm / 6.53 in (the width of this red box).

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := f_i^{IA,L}([t, t], P, B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])) \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_x\} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{x}_0^L := \mathbf{x}^{IA,L}(P),$$

and analogously for f_i^U and \mathbf{x}_0^U . (Here f_i^L does not actually depend on \mathbf{p} , so the minimization in Theorem 1 with respect to \mathbf{p} is trivial.)

- If in Theorem 1 we define:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := \inf\{f_i(t, \mathbf{p}, \zeta) : \zeta \in B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])\},$$

and analogously for f_i^U , then we immediately recover the bounding method of (Singer and Barton 2006, Corollary 2.6).

- Suppose that, for each $t \in I$, we have access to a convex relaxation $f_i^{cv}(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ of each component $f_i(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ of the right-hand side of (1), and an analogous concave relaxation f_i^{cc} . Then, if in Theorem 1 we define:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := \inf\{f_i^{cv}(t, \mathbf{p}, \zeta) : \zeta \in B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])\},$$

then we recover our previous convex relaxation-based method (Cao and Khan 2021). In particular, this formulation permits state bounds to be constructed from the α BB relaxations of f (Adjiman et al. 1998).

4.3. Obtaining new bounding methods

In addition to the established approaches we recovered above in our bounding framework, we can also obtain several new bounding methods. Here we present two categories of these relaxations: one that employs the generalized McCormick relaxations summarized in Section 4.1, and one based on the recent *edge-concave relaxations* of Hasan (2018), also summarized in Section 4.1. At this point, we note without further exploration that our new framework is compatible with the *a priori* enclosures described by Shen and Scott (2020).

4.3.1. New generalized-McCormick-based state bounds In the setup described in Section 2, suppose that \mathbf{x}_0 and f are amenable to interval analysis, and are thus also amenable to the generalized McCormick relaxations summarized in Section 4.1. Suppose that these functions are compositions of locally Lipschitz continuous operations. Then, each of the following alternative choices of f^L/f^U satisfies the requirements of Theorem 1.

1. For each i , define:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := f_i^{GM,cv} \left(([t, t], [t, t]), \quad (P, P), \quad (B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]), [\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]) \right),$$

and analogously for f_i^U . Observe that f_i^L is independent of its \mathbf{p} argument, simplifying the embedded optimization problem in (3).

2. For each i , define:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := f_i^{GM,cv} \left(([t, t], [t, t]), \quad ([\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}], P), \quad (B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]), [\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]) \right),$$

and analogously for f_i^U .

3. For each i , define:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := \min_{\zeta \in [\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]} f_i^{GM,cv} \left(([t, t], [t, t]), \quad ([\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}], P), \quad ([\zeta, \zeta], B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])) \right), \quad (4)$$

and analogously for f_i^U . Observe that this “min” naturally combines with the “min” in (3).

Each of these three approaches does indeed provide enclosing dynamics about \mathbf{x} ; this follows directly from the inclusion monotonicity properties of the generalized McCormick relaxations developed by Scott et al. (2011), Wechsung et al. (2015). Hence, each choice yields corresponding state bounds according to Theorem 1. To our knowledge, this work is the first time in which the convex relaxation component of the generalized McCormick relaxations have been used to furnish state bounds.

Moreover, we also immediately conclude the following statement from the inclusion monotonicity properties of the generalized McCormick relaxations. If any of these state bounds is used in the approach of Scott and Barton (2013) for generating convex/concave relaxations of $\mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p})$ with respect to \mathbf{p} , and if generalized McCormick relaxations are also used to construct the functions u/o in that relaxation approach, then the discrete transitions of (Scott and Barton 2013, Equations 33 and 34) will never occur; the right-hand side of each differential equation in (Scott and Barton 2013, Equation 33) will always take the upper value in its defining case-based “if statement”. Hence, we circumvent the Scott-Barton relaxations’ discontinuous switches in a completely different way to Ye and Scott (2024).

Observe that in the second and third approaches above, the embedded minimization/maximization problems in (3) become bound-constrained convex nonlinear programs (NLPs) in general, which are equivalent to their respective Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) optimality conditions (as discussed e.g. by Rockafellar (1996)), since they satisfy the Linear Constraint Qualification. We note that in this case, emerging dynamic complementarity solvers such as SICONOS (Acary and Pérignon 2007) may be able to solve the state bounding system (3) in its KKT complementarity form without having to solve an optimization problem at each right-hand side evaluation.

4.3.2. New edge-concave-based state bounds Following Hasan (2018), suppose in the setup of Section 2 that \mathbf{f} is twice-continuously differentiable, and that an edge-concave underestimator $f_i^{EC,L}(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ and an edge-convex overestimator $f_i^{EC,U}(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ are available for each component $f_i(t, \cdot, \cdot)$ at each time $t \in I$. Then, in Theorem 1 we may set:

$$f_i^L(t, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U) := \min \{ f_i^{EC,L}(t, \mathbf{p}, \zeta) : \zeta \in B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U]) \}.$$

and similarly for f_i^U ; this choice evidently exhibits enclosing dynamics and is locally Lipschitz continuous. Thus, Theorem 1 implies that state bounds may be obtained as the unique solution of the following coupled ODE system: for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n_x\}$ and $\mathbf{p} \in P$:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_i^L &= \min_{\substack{\mathbf{p} \in P \\ \zeta \in B_i^L([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])}} f_i^{EC,L}(t, \mathbf{p}, \zeta), & x_i^L(t_0) &= x_{0,i}^L, \\ \dot{x}_i^U &= \max_{\substack{\mathbf{p} \in P \\ \zeta \in B_i^U([\mathbf{z}^L, \mathbf{z}^U])}} f_i^{EC,U}(t, \mathbf{p}, \zeta), & x_i^U(t_0) &= x_{0,i}^U. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1 ODE solution trajectories (solid cyan) and corresponding state bounds for the example in Section 5.2, based on the approach by Harrison (1977) (dotted yellow-green), the approach from Section 4.2 based on α BB relaxations (dotted blue), and the approach from Section 4.3.2 based on edge-concave relaxations (dotted magenta).

Since this embedded minimization problem involves minimizing an edge-concave function over an interval subdomain, this minimum is attained at one corner/vertex of the feasible set. If, for example, the computational time to evaluate f_i is on the order of nanoseconds, and the combined number of states and parameters is within around 20, then this embedded minimization problem may be easily solved by direct enumeration of the feasible sets' vertices.

5. Numerical examples

This section outlines our implementation in Julia of the described methods, and presents two numerical examples that use this implementation to construct and solve the auxiliary bounding ODE (3).

5.1. Implementation

The approaches in the following examples were implemented in Julia v1.5.3 (Bezanson et al. 2017). The auxiliary system of ODEs are solved with `DifferentialEquations.jl` (Rackauckas and Nie 2017); generalized McCormick relaxations were generated with `McCormick.jl` (Wilhelm and Stuber 2020). JuMP v0.21.4 (Dunning et al. 2017) was used as the interface to optimization solvers; CPLEX v12.10 was used to solve linear programs (LPs), and IPOPT v3.13.2 was used to solve nonlinear programs (NLPs). All numerical experiments were performed on a Windows 10 machine with a 3.6 GHz Ryzen 5 2600X CPU and 24 GB memory.

5.2. Using edge-concave-based state bounds

In this section, we present an example that uses the edge-concave-based state bounding approach described in Section 4.3.2. Consider the following instance of the ODE (1), with a quadratic

Figure 2 Dependence of x_2 on p_1 (solid blue) at time $t = 5$ for the example in Section 5.3, along with corresponding convex/concave relaxations based on the approach of Scott and Barton (2013), with state-bounds provided by a Harrison-style approach (dotted green), our first bounding strategy from Section 4.3.1 (dashed red), and our third bounding strategy from Section 4.3.1 (dashed purple).

right-hand side function:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= (x_1 - p_1)^2 - (x_2 - p_1)^2, & x_1(0, \mathbf{p}) &= 2.2, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= (x_1 - p_2)^2 - (x_2 - p_2)^2, & x_2(0, \mathbf{p}) &= 1.8, \end{aligned}$$

for $\mathbf{p} \in P := [-2, 2] \times [-1, 3]$, over a duration $[t_0, t_f] := [0, 0.2]$. Figure 1 illustrates solution trajectories $t \mapsto \mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p})$ for several values of $\mathbf{p} \in P$, along with several state bounds that we computed: bounds based on interval analysis by Harrison (1977), bounds generated using the approach from Section 4.2 based on α BB relaxations, and bounds generated using the approach from Section 4.3.2 based on edge-concave relaxations. Observe that in this case, the new edge-concave-based bounds are significantly tighter than the other considered state bounds. As a proof of concept, the α BB-based bounds' right-hand sides' embedded optimization problems were solved using a quadratic programming solver whenever the right-hand side was evaluated by the ODE solver; the other methods did not require an external optimization solver and required vastly less CPU time to evaluate.

5.3. Using generalized-McCormick-based state bounds

As we mentioned earlier, a primary application of state bounds is to aid in the construction of convex relaxations for use in global optimization applications, via (for example) the ODE relaxation approach of Scott and Barton (2013). Thus, consider a biochemical process model adapted from Bastin and Dochain (1990), and previously considered in a convex relaxation context by Lin and Stadtherr (2006). This model is the following instance of (1):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= (\mu - 0.18)x_1, & x_1(0, \mathbf{p}) &= 0.82, \\ \dot{x}_2 &= 0.36(5.7 - x_2) - 10.53\mu x_1, & x_2(0, \mathbf{p}) &= 0.8, \end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\mu := \frac{1.2x_2}{p_2 + x_2 + p_1x_2^2},$$

for parameters $\mathbf{p} \in P := [0.4, 0.6] \times [7.0, 7.2]$, over a duration $[t_0, t_f] := [0, 5]$. Suppose we wish to generate convex/concave relaxations of $\mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{p})$ with respect to \mathbf{p} at each t .

Figure 2 shows a cross-section of our implementation's results at $t = 5$, pertaining to the dependence of x_2 on p_1 . The final states of (1) are shown for this instance, along with corresponding convex/concave relaxations by the established approach of Scott and Barton (2013) based on Harrison-style state bounds, and based on our first and third state bounding strategies from Section 4.3.1. Observe that the first state bounding strategy ultimately yielded relaxations that coincide with the original strategy of Scott and Barton (2013), though our strategy required approximately 30% less CPU time to evaluate relaxation values, presumably due to our bounding and relaxation ODEs having right-hand sides involving calls to the same functions f_i^L . The third state bounding strategy yielded significantly tighter relaxations, at the expense of having to solve the embedded optimization problems of (4).

6. Conclusions

Theorem 1 presented a new state bounding framework for solution trajectories of the parametric ODE (1), and we have shown that several established methods and useful new methods are directly represented within this framework. Future work will involve searching for additional new methods in the framework, and formally incorporating and implementing the *a priori* enclosures discussed by Shen and Scott (2020).

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